

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCERS IN PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM IN JORDAN

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Abstracts

This study examines the effect of social media influencers on encouraging sustainable tourism practices amongst social media customers of Jordan. Grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the study incorporates the digital influencer properties, content quality, source credibility, and influencer engagement as antecedents of the tourists' attitude toward sustainable tourism and their intentions to engage in it. A quantitative method was applied, and data were collected from 250 current social media users following travel influencers. A Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was applied to test the proposed relationships. The study findings showed that content quality and perceived source credibility have significant and positive and positive impacts on both attitude and behavioral intentions, while influencer engagement has a small but negative effect. Attitude towards sustainable tourism was the strongest predictor of behavioral intention, as is in line with the central role of attitude in TPB. The outcomes provide theoretical contributions by transplanting TPB to a digital marketing context and supply useful implications for brand marketing, tourism administrators, and policymakers wanting to mobilize sustainable tourist behavior via digital effect styles.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism, Social Media Influencers, Content Quality, Source Credibility, Influencer Engagement, Jordan.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the tourism industry has started to adopt sustainability as a key business strategy in reaction to rising environmental worries, shifting consumer choices, and the growing trend of accountable travel. As destinations seek to harmonize tourism development plans with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), digital communication channels have increasingly gained importance in encouraging the adoption of sustainable tourism practices by marketing sustainable tourism behaviors [1]. Among these digital instruments, social media influencers (SMIs) have contributed to influencing tourists' attitudes and intentions by producing engaging, relatable, and persuasive content [2]. Their supposed credibility, quality articles, and social interaction help to alter public views and advertise ecotourism options [3].

Given that Jordan is a country rich in cultural and environmental endowments and highly reliant on tourism as a lifeline to economic growth, sustainable tourism promotion is a challenge as much as a chance [4]. The Jordanian government and private sector have begun to implement several initiatives to promote responsible tourism practices, but there has been little knowledge of how social media can support these initiatives. Hitherto, research on SMIs and consumer behavior across domains such as fashion, health, and hospitality [5], [6] concerning the specific context of sustainable tourism behavior (STB) has been neglected. This is particularly poignant in growing tourism economies such as

Jordan, where the influence of influencer marketing is swiftly growing but empirically is still underdeveloped within the sustainability landscape [7].

The study investigates how three defining characteristics of social media influencers interact with tourists' sustainable tourism attitudes, together with their subsequent behavioral intentions. The study uses the theory of planned behavior [8] to show that attitudes are the main factor that changes the impact of influencers into intentions for sustainable tourism. This study integrates TPB theory with digital marketing and influencer theory constructs to build tourism behavior theory and provide useful marketing guidance to sustainability promotion for tourism marketers and destination management organizations, and policymakers through influencer strategies.

Accordingly, this paper seeks to answer two main research questions:

RQ1: How do social media influencer characteristics (source credibility, content quality, and influencer engagement) influence tourists' attitudes toward sustainable tourism in Jordan?

RQ2: To what extent do attitudes toward sustainable tourism affect tourists' sustainable tourism behavioral intentions?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Source Credibility

The theory of communication uses source credibility as a core principle to discuss how trustworthy and expert communicators are perceived within their specific field [9]. The acceptability of content sources has become a crucial digital marketing phenomenon across social media platforms because consumers now depend on influencer recommendations to make their choices. Influencers who establish expertise and authenticity receive greater success from their audience persuasion efforts [10]. The study findings from [6], [11] discovered that trustworthy influencers strongly affect how followers think and what they intend to purchase. Social media influencers who establish credibility in tourism influence how destinations get perceived and affect decision-making choices related to travel [12]. The process of making sustainable choices requires both knowledge and personal values, so the trustworthiness of information sources proves critical in developing tourists' environmentally conscious conduct [13].

2.2 Content Quality

The quality of content presented by influencers consists of multiple dimensions, including the value addition and information validity, as well as its accuracy and originality. Quality content has better chances of retaining viewer attention while creating trust [14]. Social media influencers who present informative and visually engaging authentic content develop a more effective positive attitude transformation in their users, according to [15]. Through inviting content delivery of sustainable values combined with cultural sensibility and behavioral responsibility, influencers effectively guide how tourists perceive

sustainability in the travel industry [16]. The combination of emotionally compelling and story-based content has been discovered to invoke moral assessment while enabling greater environmental involvement [17]. The study indicates that sustainable tourism attitudes will be greatly affected by the quality of tourism content that consumers encounter.

2.3 Influencer Engagement

Influencer engagement measures the extent of interactive audience contact those influencers establish through their comments and replies, as well as stories and mutual experiences. Social media influencers create parasocial bonds to generate intimacy with their followers because they replace traditional celebrity endorsements with artificial friendships [18], [19]. Persuasive power and authentic appearance increase when engagement between influencers and their audience reaches higher levels [20]. The active involvement of influencers enables them to produce collaborative, sustainable stories with their followers, which leads to eco-friendly travel options becoming both appealing and reachable [21]. Fortunately, the interactive nature of queries and dialogue between influencers helps them to steer tourists toward environmentally friendly choices. Active engagement between influencers and their audience has a positive impact on developing sustainable tourism attitudes, according to the proposed hypothesis.

2.4 Sustainable Tourism Attitude

The theory of planned behavior considers attitude as its essential construct because it represents how individuals evaluate specific behaviors either positively or negatively [8]. Tourism participants express sustainable tourism attitudes through their assessment of environmental preservation, combined with cultural value appreciation, and local community welfare in their travel planning. Multiple studies prove that beliefs from within and messages shared by influencers jointly form attitudes [22], [23]. Research investigations within green tourism settings show that people who demonstrate pro-environmental beliefs choose sustainable travel practices [24]. Successful communication of sustainable tourism benefits by influencers enables them to convert theoretical sustainability elements into specific personal motivations [25], [26]. The connection between influencer characteristics and behavioral results operates through sustainable tourism attitude, which serves as a mediating factor.

2.5 Sustainable Tourism Intentions

As the most immediate antecedent of actual behavior, behavior intention (i.e., capability construct) is also defined as an individual's preparedness to 'do' a given behavior [8]. However, in sustainable tourism, intentions may be to opt for eco-certified accommodations, engage in low-impact activities, or support local businesses. Attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and social norms, as well as external digital influences [27], [28], such as attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and social norms, are factors that affect sustainable tourism intentions. Studies in the past have discovered that persuasive communication, i.e., persuasive messages given by trusted online sources, such as

influencers, can increase personal intention to engage in sustainable behavior [29], [30]. Therefore, the implications of influencer-induced attitudes on the behavioral intentions in tourism have to be investigated.

2.6 Theoretical Foundation: Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

This study is based on the Theory of Planned Behavior [8], which is currently inconsistent, a community of practice, and widespread in the areas of psychology, consumer behavior, and sustainable tourism. The first component of TPB is that an individual's behavioral intention (i.e., the main determinant) is most immediate upon actual behavior and that that intention is a function of three key factors: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

Although the Theory of Planned Behavior has been used successfully to explain what behavioral intentions are in a wide range of tourism, there is increasing recognition that the digital environment, particularly social media, has contributed to the formation of such intentions from different dimensions. Thus far, traditional TPB-based cognitions like attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control have been considered as the main antecedents for intention [8], [31]. Nevertheless, in the context of contemporary communication, there is a strong predictor of these internal processes, namely, social media influencers.

Social media influencers (SMIs) are believed to influence followers' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors by their opinionated sharing of lifestyle-oriented, visual, and emotionally engaging content. There are several factors underlying the impact that they can have, starting from how credible they are as sources of information, how good the content that they produce is, and the degree to which they interact and engage with the audience. These characteristics have the potential to form behavioral beliefs that, according to TPB, are central to attitude formation. Therefore, the characteristics of influencers can be external cues of the intention of sustainable travel behavior and may lead to positive evaluations of sustainable travel behavior, which in turn will increase the intention to act sustainably [6].

Similar to previous studies that extend TPB, attitude toward sustainable tourism is extended in this study by including three key influencer-related constructs (source credibility, content quality, and influencer engagement) as antecedents of attitude toward sustainable tourism. These variables contribute to how people see and evaluate the messages of sustainability in the digital content [32]. The first is the source credibility, which refers to the extent to which followers trust and internalize the message of the influencer [33]. Second, content quality is then linked to the effectiveness of the message with clarifying, useful, and emotionally appealing content. Thirdly, influencer engagement enhances the relational closeness and parasocial interaction and improves message receptivity. Collectively, these three dimensions help define an individual's whole attitude regarding sustainable tourism [19], [20].

This is not only to affect attitude, but also it is possible to have a direct effect on behavioral intentions when followers have high trust in influencers and see influencers as lifestyle role models [34]. In line with the recent literature, which proposes that online trust can indeed sometimes be a replacement for traditional social norms or perceived behavioral control, particularly in the realm of digital choice, this extension is.

Thus, the current research contributes to TPB by suggesting that influencers' characteristics are both precursors to attitude and direct determinants of intentions in sustainable tourism [35]. More accurately, this extended model provides a richer perspective of how social media, as a digital behavioral marketplace, affects the process of making sustainability-oriented decisions by tourists [36].

This conceptual framework, based on the theoretical foundation of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and an extended model of the influencer-related constructs, hypothesizes the relationships between the study variables. Based on the framework, source credibility, content quality, and influencer engagement are proposed as key antecedents that shape tourists' attitudes toward sustainable tourism [37]. Consequently, the resulting attitudes are supposed to influence sustainable tourism practice behavioral intentions. Furthermore, Digital influence appears to function directly through these relationships because it skips the traditional cognitive pathways which connect influencer characteristics to sustainable tourism behavioral intentions. The experimental research of this project proceeds through this theoretical basis.

Figure 1: Model of Study

3. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The study adopts the theory of planned behavior (TPB) to propose the research hypotheses by influencer-related concepts that impact tourists' sustainable attitudes and intention. The hypotheses derive from the underlying theories and provide data from previous research on empirical investigations.

3.1 Source Credibility and Sustainable Tourism Attitude

The credibility of the source is very important in determining how effectively or not messages used for persuasion will work. This idea covers three particular components, as follows: expertise and trustworthiness, as well as attractiveness [10], [13]. If social media users perceive influencers as truthful authorities, they will be more likely to exhibit a belief in their content, resulting in material messaging success [38]. The credibility of influencers is a better ability of their followers to accept information being shared because it is related to important value-based issues such as sustainability. The Theory of Planned Behavior [8] External influences determine how people form their attitudes through behavioral beliefs. Tourism influencers who demonstrate strong credibility can more effectively transform beliefs, which results in developing more positive perceptions of sustainable tourism behaviors. The research conducted by [2], [39] establishes that perceptions of source credibility led to more favorable tourist evaluations in the tourism sector. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Source credibility of social media influencers positively influences tourists' attitudes toward sustainable tourism.

3.2 Content Quality and Sustainable Tourism Attitude

Social media influencers deliver quality material when they share detailed, accurate messages that users can understand clearly. High-quality communications assist influencers in creating desired consumer reactions and opinions through content that matches the audience's standards and ideals [40]. Tourists pay closer attention to sustainable tourism when influencers share educational visual content that moves them emotionally. When content combines storytelling elements with memorable visuals and educates readers, it reaches deeper into audiences for better results [38]. TPB shows that cognitive and emotional reactions create new attitudes, which affect plans to perform future actions. Therefore, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2: Content quality of social media influencers positively influences tourists' attitudes toward sustainable tourism.

3.3 Influencer Engagement and Sustainable Tourism Attitude

The amount of influencers' engagement is representative of the interaction and two-way communication between the influencer and audience. This includes replies to comments, responding to other people's comments, live sessions, and other connection-creating types of formats. Engagement by influencers with their audience strengthens perceived authenticity and relatability of influencers and thus strengthens parasocial relationships

[20], [41]. This involvement in sustainability communication is essential since it is the key to influencing audience absorption and acceptability of complex concepts like environmental conservation and ethical travel [42]. Social influence figures in the theory of planned behavior, which acknowledges the influence of social influence on behavioral beliefs, and high levels of engagement can strengthen certification of these beliefs, making sustainability personal and attainable. Consequently, this study posits the following:

H3: Influencer engagement positively influences tourists' attitudes toward sustainable tourism.

3.4 Attitude and Sustainable Tourism Intentions

TPB contains three of the most important and consistent antecedents of the behavioral intention, among which attitude is the most predominant one; it refers to an individual's positive or negative appraisals of a certain behavior [8]. An attitude toward sustainable tourism (defined as caring about the environment, local cultures, and local economies) can make it more likely to take on sustainable travel behaviors. This has been supported by several studies. For instance, [35], [43] found that people who have pro-environmental attitudes were more likely to patronize green hotels and also contribute to eco-tourism adventures, as well as reduce their ecological footprint during a period of travel. Attitude is as essential as cognitions and emotions, acting as a filter to form behavioral intentions. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Tourists' attitudes toward sustainable tourism positively influence their sustainable tourism behavioral intentions.

3.5 Source Credibility and Sustainable Tourism Intentions

In online platforms, users tend to make rapid decisions based on trust and perception, so source credibility demonstrates direct effects besides its indirect influence through attitude [44]. Users of online content trust credible influencers to both give them information and initiate behavioral changes. Within sustainable tourism, tourists make decisions for action because they trust their chosen influencer, independent of any deep attitudinal modifications [45]. Research findings indicate that credibility immediately impacts the intentions of followers, specifically in the influencer marketing space, where followers heavily depend on professional recommendations [46]. Therefore, the following direct-path hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Source credibility of social media influencers positively influences tourists' sustainable tourism behavioral intentions.

3.6 Content Quality and Sustainable Tourism Intentions

High-quality content helps people shift their beliefs and drives them to make behavior changes. Recent studies prove that messages that touch emotions and fit our needs can make us take action without passing through mental analysis first [47]. Sustainable tourism promotion depends on presenting visual information, relatable personal accounts,

and functional advice so that tourists become more attentive to responsible actions [48]. The Study has shown that this type of psychological development matches how the Elaboration Likelihood Model [49] suggests users change their behavior under high engagement or strong message conditions. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Content quality of social media influencers positively influences tourists' sustainable tourism behavioral intentions.

3.7 Influencer Engagement and Sustainable Tourism Intentions

The concept of engagement and the behavior intention are already well documented in the field of digital marketing. High levels of engagement from influencers with their audience build a community and loyalty, which increases behavioral compliance [50]. There is a possibility that tourists who feel personally connected to an influencer will imitate what he/she does, such as imitating sustainable travel behaviors [41]. Finally, engaged influencers can offer real-time feedback and encouragement to fuel the tourist's confidence and willingness to act [51]. The dynamics foster TPB's notion of perceived behavioral control, namely, encouragement from others increases a person's belief in their ability to perform a behavior. Thus, the final hypothesis is presented as follows:

H7: Influencer engagement positively influences tourists' sustainable tourism behavioral intentions.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative, cross-sectional research design to investigate the role of social media influencers in promoting sustainable tourism in Jordan. It is appropriate for investigating the structural association among many variables extracted from a more theoretical framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). Quantitative methodology allows the collection of empirical data from a large audience for testing of proposed hypotheses and evaluation of the measurement and structural models using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM).

These two individuals will serve as the targets of this study, namely Jordanian individuals 18 years and above who use social media platforms and follow at least one travel- or tourism-related influencer on social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. These people are a meaningful portion of the population who are highly exposed to influencer-generated content and are likely to be influenced to undertake sustainable tourism behaviors through digital messaging.

In light of the increase of domestic and regional tourists in Jordan, this population provides enriching information about the changing of consciousness that is related to the concept of sustainability in a digital environment. Since we desire data quality and relevance, this is a non-probability purposive sampling method.

This technique allows the researcher to deliberately select participants who will meet specific criteria associated with the research needs. (1) Are social media users, (2) Jordan residents or Jordanians, then (3) adherents of at least one social media digital travel influencer? Because this sampling approach is particularly useful in behavioral studies, where working with social media and analyzing perceptions within a digitally engaged audience, as opposed to the general population, it is not feasible to generalize the study results to the population.

According to [52], and for PLS-SEM analysis in models with multiple structural paths, a minimum sample size of 150 to 300 respondents is needed. Therefore, this study attempts to gather data from around 250 respondents who will complete the survey in a valid manner for statistical sufficiency and model consistency. Taken online, a self-administered online questionnaire is used to collect data through multiple digital channels (Facebook tourism groups, influencer pages, travel-related online communities, etc.).

With real-time response collection and wide reach, this is a cost-efficient method. The survey is written in both Arabic and English so that it is in a form that is as clear and inclusive as two translators' back translations based on the semantic and conceptual equivalence in the two versions of the languages. The questionnaire is voluntary, and electronic informed consent is given at the beginning of completion of the questionnaire to maintain ethical standards of research.

At the beginning, there is a filtering question to check that participants follow at least one travel influencer before beginning the survey. The items of the questionnaire are adapted from established, validated scales in the literature and thus measure several of the constructs of the study. Each statement is captured in the form of a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Items are adapted from [10] to obtain a measure of source credibility based on the dimensions of trustworthiness, expertise, and attractiveness.

The items used to measure content quality are adapted from [14] regarding the relevance, clarity, and usefulness of the content posted by the influencer. Based on items taken from [20] indexing influencer engagement as the perceived level of interaction and responsiveness, items are constructed for assessing influencer engagement. Sustainable tourism attitude was measured using items from [22] and sustainable tourism intentions were measured with a scale from [24], i.e., willingness to practice sustainable tourism practices.

The survey items are tested with a small sample ($n = 30$) to determine if the survey items are clear and reliable. The results are based on which minor adjustments are made to make items relevant and linguistically clear. Cronbach's alpha is used to assess reliability and is considered to have acceptable values for internal consistency if values exceed 0.70.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

Data is analyzed using SmartPLS 4.0 software to perform Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). This method is selected due to its suitability for complex models involving latent variables, its robustness with non-normal data, and its capacity to assess both direct and indirect (mediated) relationships among constructs. The analysis is conducted in two stages. First, the measurement model is assessed for internal consistency reliability (using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability), convergent validity (using Average Variance Extracted AVE), and discriminant validity (using the Fornell–Larcker criterion and HTMT ratio). Second, the structural model is evaluated to test the hypothesized relationships through path coefficient analysis using bootstrapping (5000 subsamples).

Additional model metrics, such as the coefficient of determination (R^2). Mediating effects of attitude toward sustainable tourism are also tested to determine the indirect influence of influencer-related constructs on behavioral intentions. This methodological approach provides a rigorous framework for validating the extended TPB model in the context of digital tourism promotion and contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of social media influencers in shaping sustainable tourism behavior in Jordan. The distributed online survey provided a total of 250 valid responses. We further quizzed these respondents to uncover their demographic composition.

This background information about the sample will help complete this analysis and ensure this sample is representative of the population of concern (active social media users in Jordan who follow travel influencers). **Table 1** provides a summary of the respondents' demographic profile.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Sample

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	110	44
	Female	140	56
Age Group	18–24 years	75	30
	25–34 years	95	38
	35–44 years	50	20
	45 years and above	30	12
Education Level	High School	35	14
	Bachelor's Degree	155	62
	Master's or Higher	60	24
Monthly Income	Less than 500 JOD	85	34
	500–999 JOD	110	44
	1000 JOD and above	55	22
Social Media Usage	Less than 2 hours/day	40	16
	2–4 hours/day	120	48
	More than 4 hours/day	90	36
Follows Travel Influencers	Yes	250	100

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6. MEASUREMENT MODEL ASSESSMENT

The evaluation of the measurement model established reliability and validity for all latent constructs as well as their discrimination from other model variables. The assessment process maintains both accurate measurement and consistent measurement of constructs while confirming the unique nature of constructs within the model. Internal consistency reliability was measured through the analysis of Cronbach's alpha, together with Composite Reliability (CR). Research indicates that threshold values higher than 0.70 represent acceptance for both indicators, according to [53]. The established results demonstrated that all measurement instruments demonstrated reliability through their values surpassing the recommended threshold. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) served as the measure to evaluate convergent validity. An average variance extracted value above 0.50 indicates that a construct accounts for more than half of its indicator variances, according to [54]. All Average Variance Extracted values surpassed the suggested threshold, which confirmed adequate convergent validity of the study. The evaluation for discriminant validity used a combination of the Fornell-Larcker criterion with the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). The Fornell-Larcker criterion should demonstrate that each construct's square root AVE exceeds all of its model correlations with other constructs. The results supported this condition. The HTMT values between all pairs of constructs remained below 0.85, which reinforced the discriminant validity assessment. The measurement model passes tests for reliability and validity through these results, thus producing an effective basis for proceeding to hypothesis testing in the structural model phase of analysis.

Table 2: Factor loadings.

Constructs	Items	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	(AVE)
Content Quality	CQ_1	0.797	0.778	0.794	0.856	0.598
	CQ_2	0.721				
	CQ_3	0.775				
	CQ_4	0.798				
Influencer Engagement	IE_1	0.712	0.743	0.781	0.852	0.659
	IE_2	0.845				
	IE_3	0.869				
Source Credibility	SC_1	0.820	0.858	0.860	0.904	0.701
	SC_2	0.879				
	SC_3	0.808				

	SC_4	0.842				
Sustainable Tourism Attitude	STA_1	0.822	0.759	0.771	0.847	0.581
	STA_2	0.788				
	STA_3	0.702				
	STA_4	0.730				
Sustainable Tourism Intentions	STI_1	0.804	0.756	0.773	0.843	0.574
	STI_2	0.725				
	STI_3	0.744				
	STI_4	0.756				

The analysis shows that every factor loading surpasses 0.70, which demonstrates satisfactory discrimination power of individual measurement items. The measurement model shows robustness because all constructs achieved acceptable levels of internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha > 0.70) and composite reliability (CR > 0.70), together with convergent validity (AVE > 0.50) based on the criteria of [53].

Figure 2: Results of the Measurement Model

Table 3: HTMT

	Content Quality	Influencer Engagement	Source Credibility	Sustainable Tourism Attitude	Sustainable Tourism Intentions
Content Quality					
Influencer Engagement	0.645				
Source Credibility	0.553	0.517			
Sustainable Tourism Attitude	0.518	0.579	0.621		
Sustainable Tourism Intentions	0.572	0.805	0.608	0.535	

According to [55], Satisfactory discriminant validity exists when HTMT values stay under 0.85. As Table 3 shows

Table 4: Fornell and Larcker

	Content Quality	Influencer Engagement	Source Credibility	Sustainable Tourism Attitude	Sustainable Tourism Intentions
Content Quality	0.773				
Influencer Engagement	0.780	0.812			
Source Credibility	0.459	0.416	0.837		
Sustainable Tourism Attitude	0.760	0.749	0.502	0.762	
Sustainable Tourism Intentions	0.633	0.607	0.495	0.709	0.752

All of the diagonal values (AVE) are greater than the intercorrelations, showing there is discriminant validity as per [54] criterion. As Table 4 shows.

Table 5: R² and R-square adjusted

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Sustainable Tourism Attitude	0.805	0.803
Sustainable Tourism Intentions	0.790	0.789

The model achieves solid explanatory power according to R-square values because it accounts for 80.5% of sustainable tourism attitude variance and 79.0% of sustainable tourism intentions variance [56].as table 5 shows

Figure 3: Structural Model Result

7. STRUCTURAL MODEL EVALUATION

The structural model is used to determine associations between study constructs after confirming the measurement model's reliability and validity. The assessment determined path coefficient values and model explanatory power using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) with a bootstrapping procedure running 5,000 subsamples to verify each path significance. The study analysis confirmed the existence of all theoretical relationships between constructs, with p values falling below 0.01. The results from Table 6, Path Coefficients and Hypotheses Testing, demonstrate that content quality stands as the main positive driver behind sustainable tourism attitude and behavioral intentions because tourists heavily depend on clear and relevant engaging content for forming sustainable perceptions. Sustainable tourism attitude creates a very potent impact on behavioral intentions in line with the Theory of Planned Behavior [8] since attitude stands as a primary driver of intention. The study confirms that source credibility produces measurable positive outcomes on both attitude and intention since trusted influencers deliver relevant expertise to their audience. The involvement of influencers produced negligible negative effects that affected both outcome variables in the assessment. The results demonstrate how excessive influencer contact that lacks substance can potentially undermine message trustworthiness, along with raising doubts about authenticity. The model demonstrated strong capability to explain the research

data. The model explained 80.5% of sustainable tourism attitude while explaining 79% of sustainable tourism intentions based on the reported R² values. The model demonstrates high predictive accuracy through values that indicate an ability to predict up to 80.5% and 79.0% of the variance present in the two key constructs.

Table 6: Hypothesis Testing (Path Coefficients – β)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Content Quality -> Sustainable Tourism Attitude	0.965	0.965	0.053	18.284	0.000
Content Quality -> Sustainable Tourism Intentions	0.857	0.859	0.049	17.655	0.000
Influencer Engagement -> Sustainable Tourism Attitude	-0.150	-0.151	0.054	2.791	0.005
Influencer Engagement -> Sustainable Tourism Intentions	-0.133	-0.134	0.048	2.782	0.005
Source Credibility -> Sustainable Tourism Attitude	0.121	0.121	0.033	3.647	0.000
Source Credibility -> Sustainable Tourism Intentions	0.107	0.108	0.030	3.632	0.000
Sustainable Tourism Attitude -> Sustainable Tourism Intentions	0.889	0.890	0.009	98.919	0.000

The statistical testing conducted on hypothesized relationships revealed significance at $p < 0.01$ in accordance with Table 6 – Path Coefficients and Hypotheses Testing. Content quality produced the most significant influence on sustainable tourism attitude and behavioral intention, yet influencer engagement generated a minor negative outcome. The effects of sustainable tourism attitude surpassed other variables to deliver the most substantial impact on intentions.

8. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The study data reveals important conclusions about how social media influencers affect visitor sustainable conduct in Jordan through the Theory of Planned Behavior principles (Ajzen, 1991). The statistical significance of all model relationships proved the conceptual và theoretical constructs correct.

Sustainable tourism attitude demonstrated a statistically significant effect on behavioral intention, thus confirming TPB's main tenet about behavioral intention resulting from individual attitudes towards specific conduct [8]. Previous studies in tourism research demonstrated that environmental attitude formed favorable predictors of sustainable travel decisions [22], [24]. Those who have positive perspectives about sustainable tourism tend to perform actions demonstrating both ecological stewardship and cultural respect.

Content quality retained the position of the most critical antecedent, which substantially affects both tourist attitudes toward environmental behavior and their intentions to act accordingly. Multiple scholarly works demonstrate the power of content created by influencers when it has relevant professional design elements that engage audiences [2], [14]. Ultra-professional content functions twofold by teaching while hitting emotions that lead viewers to adopt new perspectives toward environmentally friendly actions. The research outcome proves that visual storytelling combined with authentic communication and clear messaging serves as a key factor to promote environmentally conscious travel practices.

Influencer marketing demonstrated that source credibility produced beneficial effects on both attitude and intention, just like this study [5], [6]. The credibility that followers assign to influencers boosts their message reception because followers trust influencers to share responsible behavioral content, which includes ecotourism and ethical purchasing decisions.

The involvement of influencers demonstrated a slight but unfavorable influence on both sustainable tourism attitude formation and visitor intentions. The current study produced different results from prior research by discovering negative relations between influencer engagement and persuasive effects [20], [57]. Followers tend to lose their perception when influencers use excessive repetitive actions or promote excessively, which leads to audience skepticism. Research evidence demonstrates that purposeful involvement stands above other methods in achieving sustainability messaging outcomes through social media.

8.1 Theoretical Implications

The study expands the Theory of Planned Behavior by introducing source credibility, content quality engagement as factors that shape behavioral beliefs. The research provides deeper contextual knowledge about digital social media cues that affect behavioral beliefs while assessing intentions within tourism sustainability areas [58], [59]. The model functions to connect traditional behavioral theory with modern digital influence techniques.

8.2 Practical Implications

Tourism marketers, alongside Jordanian NGOs and policymakers, should consider working with trusted influencers who create detailed content that evokes emotions because this proves to be a successful approach for developing sustainable tourism

markets. Tourism marketing campaigns need to promote educational material that both inspires and matches the cultural and natural aspects of the area. A simultaneous requirement exists to provide influencers with guidance about maintaining genuine interaction alongside guarding against commercialization that could weaken message effectiveness.

9. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers studied how social media influencers can drive sustainable tourism behavior adoption among users of social media platforms based in Jordan. Obtaining its framework from the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research design used content quality and source credibility along with influencer engagement as antecedents that shape tourists' attitudes, which determine their behavioral intentions. The analysis of 250 valid respondents using PLS-SEM revealed all predicted relationships as significant, and content quality, together with sustainable tourism attitude, demonstrated the most powerful effects on intention.

Research findings expand TPB adoption in digital marketing fields, along with clarifying how influencer-related aspects affect pro-environmental behavior in tourism domains. The positive impact of content quality and source credibility on both attitude and intention appeared stronger than influencer engagement, which surprisingly displayed a small but negative relationship within sustainability messaging digital contexts.

The study provides valuable information that directly pertains to developing economies like Jordan, since their tourism industry drives economic progress, and sustainable approaches gain greater prominence in national policies. This presented framework provides tourism authorities and NGOs, and digital marketers with an operational method to create successful, sustainable behavior promotion strategies through credible influencer selection and high-quality content creation.

9.1 Recommendations

The study presents multiple recommendations based on its findings.

1. The tourism boards, together with sustainability-focused organizations, should work with content creators whose material consistently showcases compelling visuals and helpful knowledge along with emotional depth. Sustainable behavior, together with attitude changes, has its strongest potential through this strategy.
2. Partnering with influencers who demonstrate credibility through expertise, along with sustainability value alignment, will create positive effects on message acceptance and subsequent behavioral changes.
3. Deep or numerous influencer interactions should be avoided to protect their credibility. Learning organizations must give influencers essential training related to maintaining both professional and genuine interaction methods.

4. The adaptation of content and messages must be synchronized to the formulas that are local cultures by distinct policies for every reigning demographic. Digital environments have distinct fancies that make content successful in one platform but fail in another.
5. Public authorities should focus on establishing digital standards combined with educational courses where influencers can pass on sustainable tourism knowledge and ethics through effective sustainability practices.

10. FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Future studies need to examine both the psychological constructs of TPB, like subjective norms and perceived behavioral control, and possible mediating effects of trust, alongside perceived authenticity. Research of influencers in chronological order could track the evolution of their strategy ahead of observing lasting results on true behavioral modification. The study that enhances comparative analysis across various cultural and regional contexts may enhance the generalization power of the outcome of this study.

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